

ANALYSIS OF EUROPEAN UNION IMPLICATION IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROMOTION BY MEANS OF THE SUPPORT NETWORKS

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Abstract

Purpose-This study started from the observation of the multidimensional implication of European Union in entrepreneurship promotion with present effects in each member state. In this context, from the multitude of strategies, projects and actions, by this research we followed the identification of the role attributed to the dimension of the support networks in entrepreneurship promotion at EU level.

Methodology/approach-In the realization of the study we used of a qualitative methodology, considering the fact that the research has an exploratory character, and as a research technique we made used of analysis of content of the texts, of European Commission's official publications, limited in time, respectively only the publications of the 2020 year.

Findings- Following the performed analysis we found out that from the perspective of the European Commission the support networks are important pillars of the entrepreneurship promotion, being a critical dimension of the entrepreneurship promotion.

Research limitations/implication - The process of research was limited by lack of access to information related to traffic on these online platforms.

Practical implications- Nevertheless, by means of the performed research we identified each support network with role in entrepreneurship promotion allowing dissemination of information regarding these, as well as the observation from a different perspective of the online platforms made available by the European Commission, as resources of entrepreneurship promotion.

Key words: "entrepreneurship", "support networks", "European Union"

Chapter 1. Plan of action Entrepreneurship 2020-Restart of the Enterprise spirit in Europe

Building of an economy in service of citizens is a priority of European Commission in whose direction this achieves different actions. An economy in citizens' service supposes a series of aspects, among which entrepreneurship has its role, as source of innovation, competitiveness and of creation of new jobs, a source of economic growth. Thus, among the primordial objectives of the European Commission there is the entrepreneurship promotion in European Union. For this the Commission elaborated and adopted in the year 2013 *the Action plan for entrepreneurship 2020-Restart of entrepreneurship spirit in Europe*, with the target to develop the entrepreneurship potential, eliminated the obstacles and revolutionized the culture of entrepreneurship in EU.

The plan was built as a natural consequence of the progresses registered after the adoption in the year 2008 of Small Business Act-with role in promotion of entrepreneurship spirit, of the review of the year 2011 of this and following the adoption in October 2012 of the Communication regarding the industrial

policy. Thus, the plan was proposed as a continuation of the objective of supporting the entrepreneurship in Europe through a new vision and action.

The plan is based on three strategies: development of education and training in the field of entrepreneurship; creation of adequate business environment; models and implication of some specific groups [*THE ACTION PLAN FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP 2020*].

The initiatives by which the European Commission promotes the entrepreneurship are contained on short in the Action plan for entrepreneurship 2020-*Restart of the entrepreneurship spirit in Europe* adopted in January 2013.

Thus, the Plan proposes three great directions in immediate intervention:

1. Education and entrepreneurship training in order to support the growth and creation of enterprises;
2. Strengthening of framework conditions for entrepreneurs by removing of existing structural barriers and by supporting of entrepreneurs in the key stages of the enterprises life cycle;
3. Stimulating of entrepreneurship culture in Europe: training of new generations of entrepreneurs.

Chapter 2. Promotion of entrepreneurship continues to be an adequate answer for the economic crises

At the beginning of year 2020 Europe was still recovering after the financial crisis from the year 2008-2012 although it passed quite a big period since that moment. The year 2020 is probably the biggest attempt with which the economies and population confront at the European world level, in recent 50 years in the context of pandemic of Covid 19. At the outbreak of Covid 19 crisis, the echoes of the crisis from 2008-2012 had just gone out. As now, the crisis a decade ago occurred after some consecutive years of economic growth. Propagation of the effects of the crisis and the response policy in the two contexts but they tend to differ. In 2008-2012 the risk of economic crisis outlined with a year before, while now in only 2-3 months.

Ten years ago the recession felt gradually, but equally in relation to the economic branches, while now this had a differentiated impact. For years it has been discussing at the world level in the context of globalization of certain world threats, possible risks (bacteria resistant to antibiotics, world food crisis, noxious emissions from the air caused by transport, losing of oceans and seas biodiversity, the lost generation because of unemployment etc.), that can affect us from economic, social, health point of view. The "Global Opportunity Report 2016" of Global Compact shows us at the respective time how the global preset problems, beyond of their threat, can be transformed in business opportunities. Their resolution opens new markets to which can make for both the big companies and start-ups, small, medium and big entrepreneurs. For example the finding of resolutions for the pollution provoked by transport or for food waste can become both source of incomes and contribution for some world problems improvement.

Starting from the premise that the business is the key of economic coming to normal, the innovative, competitive entrepreneurship spirit are essential for European economic coming back to normal. In an epoch of globalization and a growth of competitiveness from the part of countries, on a prolonged period of time, the economic prosperity in European Union depends on the strong industrial basis, and not only by banking services. Europe must believe again in its capacity of innovation, creativity, are still necessary the launch of new projects, of increase the innovations in different priority fields, pre-eminently priority. Thus, Europe should put into application the real economic power, business, economic incentives.

Considering that at the level of European Union the main engine as regards the number of employed persons is represented by the small and medium enterprises sector, one of the main objectives of European Union is encouraging of this sector of activity, so that a number of more persons to become entrepreneurs, respectively creation of necessary premises so to have the possibility to develop their business. According to a study achieved by the European Commission only 37 percentages from Europeans would like to become entrepreneurs, as compared to the USA and China population where this percentage amounts to 51 percentages.

Taking into account that we are in a historical moment from the last fifty years, with a record number of unemployed people over 25 millions, the European Commission plan in the year 2020 is of restart of the entrepreneurial spirit at EU level. The European Commission strategy as regards the entrepreneurial sector is based on three important pillars:

1. Training and entrepreneurial education of quality with a view to support this sector both on the part of start-ups and as regards the existent business.
2. Creation of an environment for entrepreneurs in which these can thrive and can extend their business (facilitating of the access to different sources of financing, facilitating of the rules and procedures by applying of clear and simple regulations, development of entrepreneurship in new directions taking into account the evolution digitalization at the global level, facilitating of procedures for the bankrupt companies by granting of new chances for honest entrepreneurs.
3. New perceptions: promotion of entrepreneurship and of their success stories as examples to follow at global, local level, respectively the creation of the necessary premises and encouraging of certain categories of persons: women, seniors, respectively emigrants in view of becoming of some successful entrepreneurs, respectively of the last ones implication who are already models worthy to follow in the entrepreneurial sector in new business training and launching.

More than ever society is before some challenges that ask global solutions.

According to Eurostat, the economic decline from the European Union and euro zone is the worst since the moment when there have begun to be reported date of this type, in 1995. At the level of European Union, the economy contracted with 11,9 percentages compared to the first term and with 14,4 percentages compared to the second term of the last year, show the Eurostat data adjusted to the season. Against the background of the present crisis, the new enterprises continue to represent a key ingredient so that to assist at a revival as regards the creation of new jobs at UE level.

Chapter3. The support networks as size of the entrepreneurship promotion at the European Union level

The support networks in the form of some online platforms represent essential elements for communication achievement in the present economic environment characterized by speed. These contribute at the policies promotion, transparency insurance and have the advantage of facilitating the communication quickly and easily regardless of the place where there are interested subjects.

One of the ways of promotion of entrepreneurship by the European Commission is represented by the online available support networks. Thus, with role in ensuring the implementation of the action plan for entrepreneurship is the SME Envoys network. Other support networks and information related to entrepreneurship and IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) are: Your Europe Business Portal; Enterprise Europe Network; SME Internationalization support page; portal on Access to Finance.

SME Envoys

For the implementation of the action plan for entrepreneurship work the SME envoy networks named at the national level, with role in: promotion of IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) interests to all the governmental structures and ensure the integration of principle "think small first time" in elaborating of policies and the proposals for elaboration of regulations; ensure an interface between Commission and national factors of decision; report the SBA (the act for the little entrepreneur) adoption in EU countries, intensify efforts for distribution of information regarding the actions of policy for IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) and promote the exchange of best practices.

A concrete result of SME Envoy Network is represented by their decision of supplementing SBA WITH the programme SME-Action Programme. The programme supplies an analysis of the present situation and of the main challenges for IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) from Europe. Also, this ensures the transfer of best practices within the network SME Envoy Network and delivers direction and inspiration for different political fields relevant to IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) [European SME-action programme, 2017, <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/36142>].

Your Europe Business Portal

The portal was built for offering the possibility to entrepreneurs to have access to information and interactive services that allow them to extend their business abroad. This represents a practical guide available online, regarding the manner in which the business are done in Europe.

Information are offered in all official languages of European Union-with the exception of Irish and are delivered by the relevant departments of European Commission and completed by the authorities from each country. In addition of the supplied information ,on the platform there is the possibility of receiving personalized information by e-mail or telephone provided free of charge by the EU assistance services.

Enterprise Europe Network

The Enterprise Europe Network was created to support IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) and entrepreneurs to obtain information related to the access on market, to surpass obstacles and to indentify business partners from outside Europe.

The online platform of the network offers professional information related to the expansion and development of international market, offers support for the transformation of the innovative ideas in a commercial success and makes available expertise, contacts and events in order to offer possibility to identify business partners.

Also, the platform ensures the contact either with a connecting point of the network from a country from EU or outside EU, by selecting the state either directly with an international partner. In an easy manner the platform ensures the possibility of developing partnerships in different fields. The platform hosts also a special section where are listed offers for different collaborations of business.

SME Internationalization support page

The European Commission follows to ensure the adequate information in connection with the foreign markets and to help the enterprises to extend themselves by activities of internationalization. The main instruments used for these are: Enterprise Europe Network; EU SME Centre in China (represent an initiative of EU in order to support IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES) to develop business in China by 5 services: Knowledge Centre, Counselling Centre, Training Centre, Platform of Advocacy for IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES), Hot-Desks & Meeting Rooms); EU-Japan Centre for Industrial Cooperation; Market Access Database- provides information to enterprises that export from EU ABOUT THE IMPORT conditions from the third states; Export Helpdesk-information of assistance and access at market for the import in EU; IPR helpdesk-information and advice related to the intellectual property plus other information transmitted by the published guides.

Portal on Access to Finance

The last network with role in entrepreneurship promotion follows to grant support IMM (SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES)to receive financial support from EU part by providing of information about EU funds, EU programmes and sources of financing from each EU member state.

Conclusions

As shown in the Report regarding the evaluation of support services for entrepreneurs and new business published at the beginning of year 2020 by the European Commission and as results from the analysis of the initiatives developed in the direction of entrepreneurship promotion, the support networks represent a crucial size for entrepreneurship promotion, especially as regards the access at experts, business contacts, models, partnerships and providing of information in an easy manner.

The present context requests a special attention to the sizes of the support networks, as the online available support networks eliminate the barriers caused by the impossibility of travel of the persons and reduce the costs determined by information and establishing of some contacts personally.

Furthermore, it is important that these networks to be promoted adequately in such a way that EU citizens to be used to their use.

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COM/2011/0078 final: Review of the “Small Business Act” for Europe

<https://eurlex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri-CELEX:52011DC0078>

Practical guide to doing business in Europe

https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/index_en.htm

Enterprise Europe Network

<https://een.ec.europa.eu/>

The Market Access Database

<https://madb.europa.eu/madb/indexPubli.htm>

European Commission

<https://ec.europa.eu/>